

Detrimental Effects of Traffic Noise in Traffic Police Personnel as Assessed by Auditory Brain Stem Evoked ResponseMegha Kapoor¹, Shazia²^{1,2}Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Government Medical College, Jammu

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Megha Kapoor

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Traffic police personnel are often exposed to high levels of noise due to their occupational environment, which may adversely affect auditory function. This study aims to evaluate the detrimental effects of chronic traffic noise exposure on auditory brainstem responses (ABR) among traffic police personnel in Jammu, India.

Methods: This comparative cross-sectional study included 136 traffic police personnel with a minimum of 5 years of experience, regularly exposed to noise levels ≥ 85 dB for at least 6 hours daily. A control group of 120 age- and gender-matched individuals with no noise exposure was also assessed. ABR testing was performed using the Biologic Navigator Pro system, measuring latencies of waves I, III, and V, along with interpeak intervals. Noise exposure levels were assessed using a calibrated sound level meter.

Results: Traffic police personnel exhibited significantly prolonged latencies for waves I (1.88 ± 0.23 ms), III (4.27 ± 0.25 ms), and V (6.45 ± 0.34 ms) compared to controls ($p < 0.05$ for all). The prevalence of tinnitus and difficulty in hearing was significantly higher in the traffic police group (54.4% and 44.9%, respectively) versus controls (10.0% and 7.5%, respectively). Correlation analysis revealed significant associations between noise exposure levels and ABR latencies (r values from 0.432 to 0.541, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Chronic exposure to high traffic noise among traffic police personnel is associated with significant auditory dysfunction, as reflected by altered ABR parameters. The findings underscore the need for regular auditory assessments and protective measures to mitigate the impact of noise exposure in this occupational group.

Keywords: Traffic police, auditory brainstem response, noise exposure, tinnitus, occupational health, auditory dysfunction.

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Introduction

Noise pollution is a growing environmental hazard, particularly in urban areas with high traffic density. The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies environmental noise as a leading cause of several health issues, including cardiovascular diseases, cognitive impairment, and sleep disturbances [1].

Traffic noise, in particular, has emerged as one of the most pervasive forms of noise pollution, with detrimental effects on both the general population and occupational groups with prolonged exposure. Among the most affected occupational groups are traffic police personnel, who spend several hours a day in high-traffic environments, often without adequate hearing protection. In urban settings, traffic noise can frequently exceed 85 dB, a level identified as the threshold for noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) [2]. According to the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of India, noise levels in metropolitan cities regularly exceed the permissible limits of 55-75 dB, reaching up to 90

dB or higher in high-traffic zones [3]. For instance, a 2019 report from the CPCB indicated that noise levels in traffic-heavy areas of Delhi and Mumbai were consistently over 90 dB during peak hours [3]. This sustained exposure to high noise levels puts traffic police personnel at significant risk of auditory and non-auditory health issues, including stress, fatigue, and hearing impairment [4].

The auditory system, particularly the cochlea and the auditory nerve, is highly sensitive to noise exposure. Prolonged exposure to elevated noise levels can lead to irreversible damage to the hair cells in the cochlea, resulting in sensorineural hearing loss. However, before significant hearing loss occurs, early functional changes in the auditory pathway can be detected using neurophysiological assessments such as Auditory Brainstem Evoked Response (ABR) testing [5]. ABR is a reliable, non-invasive tool that measures electrical activity in the auditory nerve and brainstem in response to

auditory stimuli [6]. It provides information about the integrity of the auditory pathway and can detect early auditory dysfunction that might not yet be apparent through conventional audiometric tests [5].

Several studies have explored the effects of noise exposure on ABR parameters. Prolonged noise exposure has been shown to increase the latencies of ABR waveforms, particularly waves I, III, and V, which represent neural activity at different levels of the auditory pathway [7]. These delayed latencies are indicative of auditory nerve and brainstem dysfunction. In a study conducted on Indian industrial workers exposed to high noise levels, significant prolongation of ABR wave latencies was observed, suggesting early neural damage due to noise [4]. Similarly, airport ground staff and military personnel exposed to loud jet engines and artillery fire have also shown abnormal ABR responses, supporting the hypothesis that chronic noise exposure adversely affects auditory processing [8].

Despite this body of research, limited attention has been given to traffic police personnel, who are chronically exposed to high-decibel noise in urban environments. Basu et al., highlighted that over 40% of traffic police officers in major cities, including Delhi and Kolkata, reported symptoms of hearing impairment and tinnitus [4]. Similarly, a survey by CPCB found that noise-induced hearing loss was prevalent among traffic police personnel in Mumbai, where noise levels during rush hours frequently crossed 90 dB [3]. Yet, there is a lack of focused studies assessing the specific impact of traffic noise on their auditory brainstem function through ABR testing. This study aimed to fill this gap by assessing the auditory brainstem responses of traffic police personnel regularly exposed to traffic noise. Through detailed ABR assessments, the study has evaluated the extent of auditory pathway dysfunction in this population and determine the potential risks of long-term exposure to traffic noise. The findings from this study could serve as a basis for preventive interventions, such as the use of protective devices and noise regulation measures, to safeguard the auditory health of traffic police personnel.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted in the department of Physiology at Tertiary Care Hospital (Government medical college, Jammu) for a period of 1 year from August 2022 to July 2023.

Study population and sample size: The study population consisted of traffic police personnel working in urban areas with high traffic density in Jammu, and a total of 136 traffic police personnel were included in the study. The inclusion criteria

for the study required participants to have a minimum of 5 years of experience, regular exposure to high traffic noise (≥ 85 dB) for at least 6 hours a day, and be aged between 25 and 55 years. Exclusion criteria included a history of pre-existing hearing disorders or ear infections, use of ototoxic medications, previous exposure to loud occupational noise in non-traffic settings such as factories or airports, and any history of neurological or psychiatric disorders.

A control group of age- and gender-matched individuals ($n = 120$) with no history of prolonged noise exposure or hearing impairments was also assessed using the same ABR protocol. These individuals were drawn from administrative personnel working indoors at Institution or Office.

Noise Exposure Assessment: Traffic noise exposure was measured using a calibrated sound level meter (SLM) in various high-traffic zones where the traffic police personnel were stationed. Measurements were taken during peak hours (8:00 AM - 12:00 PM and 4:00 PM - 8:00 PM) to assess the average noise levels. The SLM recorded noise levels in dB(A), and personnel were categorized based on their exposure duration and intensity.

Auditory Brainstem Evoked Response (ABR) Testing: Auditory Brainstem Evoked Response (ABR) testing was performed to evaluate the auditory brainstem function of the participants. The testing took place in a soundproof room in the ENT department using the Biologic Navigator Pro ABR system (Natus Medical Incorporated, USA). The following steps were followed: Surface electrodes were placed at the vertex (Cz), mastoid (M1 and M2), and forehead (ground) after skin preparation to ensure optimal contact. Click stimuli at 90 dB nHL were presented monaurally to each ear through insert earphones, and the ABR waveforms were recorded at a rate of 11.1 clicks per second. The latencies of waves I, III, and V were measured, along with interpeak intervals I-III, III-V, and I-V, with latency prolongation and changes in amplitude considered indicative of auditory dysfunction. Participants were categorized into groups based on their noise exposure duration (low: < 5 hours/day, moderate: 5-8 hours/day, high: > 8 hours/day) and intensity (> 85 dB or < 85 dB).

Data Collection and Variables: Data collection was done using semi structured proforma. Data collection focused on the primary outcome of ABR latency and interpeak intervals in traffic police personnel. Secondary outcomes included self-reported hearing issues such as tinnitus and difficulty in hearing, as well as years of service and noise exposure intensity. The independent variables were noise exposure level, duration of service, age, and sex, while the dependent variables included the

latencies of ABR waves I, III, and V, as well as the interpeak intervals (I-III, III-V, I-V).

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 20.0. Continuous variables, such as age, noise exposure levels, and ABR latencies, were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while categorical variables, such as the presence of tinnitus and difficulty in hearing, were presented as percentages. Independent t-tests were used to compare the ABR wave latencies and interpeak intervals between the exposed and control groups.

One-way ANOVA was performed to assess the effects of different noise exposure durations on ABR parameters, and Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between noise exposure intensity and ABR latency. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Ethical Considerations: The study was conducted after obtaining ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Written informed

consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Participants were assured of confidentiality and the voluntary nature of their participation.

Results

The study included 136 traffic police personnel in the exposed group and 120 participants in the control group. The mean age of the traffic police group (41.5 ± 7 years) was similar to the control group (40.2 ± 6 years), with no significant difference ($p = 0.326$). Both groups had a male predominance (91.2% vs. 95.8%, $p = 0.218$). Traffic police personnel had significantly longer service durations (13.5 ± 3.6 vs. 9.8 ± 2.5 years, $p = 0.002$) and higher noise exposure levels (89.7 ± 4.5 dB vs. 61.2 ± 8.3 dB, $p < 0.0001$). Tinnitus was more prevalent among traffic police (54.4% vs. 10.0%, $p < 0.0001$), and hearing difficulty was significantly higher in this group (44.9% vs. 7.5%, $p = 0.001$) (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (%)/ Mean \pm SD		p-value
	Exposed Group (n = 136)	Control Group (n = 120)	
Age (years)	41.5 ± 7	40.2 ± 6	0.326
Gender			
Male	124 (91.2%)	115 (95.8%)	0.218
Female	12 (8.8%)	5 (4.2%)	
Duration of Service (years)	13.5 ± 3.6	9.8 ± 2.5	0.002
Noise Exposure (dB)	89.7 ± 4.5	61.2 ± 8.3	<0.0001
Tinnitus	74 (54.4%)	12 (10.0%)	<0.0001
Difficulty in Hearing	61 (44.9%)	9 (7.5%)	0.001

ABR parameters were significantly altered in the traffic police group compared to the control group. Traffic police showed prolonged latencies in Wave I (1.88 ± 0.23 ms vs. 1.71 ± 0.17 ms, $p = 0.021$), Wave III (4.27 ± 0.25 ms vs. 4.03 ± 0.22 ms, $p = 0.012$), and Wave V (6.45 ± 0.34 ms vs. 6.01 ± 0.31 ms, $p = 0.015$). Interpeak intervals, including I-III ($p = 0.046$), III-V ($p = 0.035$), and I-V ($p = 0.017$), were also significantly longer in the traffic police group, indicating auditory pathway dysfunction likely due to prolonged noise exposure (Table 2).

Table 2: Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) Latencies and Interpeak Intervals in Exposed vs Control Groups

ABR Parameters	Mean \pm SD		p-value
	Exposed Group	Control Group	
Wave I Latency (ms)	1.88 ± 0.23	1.71 ± 0.17	0.021
Wave III Latency (ms)	4.27 ± 0.25	4.03 ± 0.22	0.012
Wave V Latency (ms)	6.45 ± 0.34	6.01 ± 0.31	0.015
Interpeak Interval I-III (ms)	2.39 ± 0.28	2.26 ± 0.20	0.046
Interpeak Interval III-V (ms)	2.18 ± 0.26	1.98 ± 0.18	0.035
Interpeak Interval I-V (ms)	4.57 ± 0.34	4.22 ± 0.28	0.017

The ABR parameters varied significantly across the different noise exposure groups (Table 3). The average noise level increased from the low (84.6 ± 3.2 dB) to the high exposure group (92.4 ± 4.5 dB, $p = 0.021$). Similarly, the duration of exposure increased from 11.2 ± 2.8 years in the low exposure group to 14.9 ± 4.0 years in the high exposure

group ($p = 0.044$). Latencies of ABR waves I, III, and V progressively increased with higher noise exposure levels. Wave I latency ranged from 1.83 ± 0.22 ms in the low exposure group to 1.94 ± 0.25 ms in the high exposure group ($p = 0.043$). Wave III latency also increased from 4.19 ± 0.24 ms to 4.33 ± 0.28 ms ($p = 0.037$), and Wave V latency

from 6.22 ± 0.31 ms to 6.55 ± 0.35 ms ($p = 0.024$). Interpeak intervals I-III, III-V, and I-V followed a similar pattern, with I-V prolonging from 4.50 ± 0.32 ms in the low exposure group to 4.62 ± 0.36

ms in the high exposure group ($p = 0.031$), suggesting increased auditory pathway dysfunction with higher noise exposure (Table 3).

Table 3: Effect of Noise Exposure Duration on ABR Parameters in Exposed Group

Variables	Mean \pm SD			p-value
	Noise Exposure Group			
	Low (n=34)	Moderate (n=72)	High (n=30)	
Average Noise Level (dB)	84.6 ± 3.2	88.3 ± 3.8	92.4 ± 4.5	0.021
Duration of Exposure (years)	11.2 ± 2.8	13.6 ± 3.2	14.9 ± 4.0	0.044
ABR Parameters				
Wave I Latency (ms)	1.83 ± 0.22	1.87 ± 0.24	1.94 ± 0.25	0.043
Wave III Latency (ms)	4.19 ± 0.24	4.25 ± 0.25	4.33 ± 0.28	0.037
Wave V Latency (ms)	6.22 ± 0.31	6.41 ± 0.33	6.55 ± 0.35	0.024
I-III Interval (ms)	2.36 ± 0.22	2.41 ± 0.26	2.45 ± 0.28	0.051
III-V Interval (ms)	2.10 ± 0.23	2.16 ± 0.25	2.24 ± 0.26	0.044
I-V Interval (ms)	4.50 ± 0.32	4.57 ± 0.34	4.62 ± 0.36	0.031

Table 4 presents the correlation between ABR parameters and noise exposure levels. A significant positive correlation was observed for all ABR latency measures and interpeak intervals, indicating that increased noise exposure is associated with longer latencies and intervals. Specifically, Wave I latency showed a correlation coefficient of 0.432 ($p = 0.023$), while Wave III and Wave V latencies had coefficients of 0.458 ($p = 0.011$) and 0.481 ($p =$

0.019), respectively. Interpeak intervals also exhibited strong correlations, with I-III at 0.424 ($p = 0.036$), III-V at 0.475 ($p = 0.024$), and I-V at 0.541 ($p = 0.013$). These findings suggest that prolonged noise exposure not only increases the latencies of the auditory brainstem response but also affects the efficiency of auditory processing, indicating potential auditory pathway dysfunction linked to chronic noise exposure.

Table 4: Correlation Between Noise Exposure Intensity and ABR Parameters in Exposed Group

ABR Parameters	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Wave I Latency (ms)	0.432	0.023
Wave III Latency (ms)	0.458	0.011
Wave V Latency (ms)	0.481	0.019
Interpeak Interval I-III (ms)	0.424	0.036
Interpeak Interval III-V (ms)	0.475	0.024
Interpeak Interval I-V (ms)	0.541	0.013

Discussion

This study assessed the effects of chronic traffic noise exposure on auditory function among traffic police personnel, revealing significant alterations in Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) parameters. The observed prolonged latencies in Waves I, III, and V, alongside increased interpeak intervals, indicate potential auditory pathway dysfunction. Specifically, the mean Wave I latency of 1.88 ms in the traffic police group aligns with findings from Zaw et al., who reported similar delays in workers exposed to industrial noise levels exceeding 85 dB [9]. Similarly, Singh et al., found that prolonged noise exposure resulted in significantly delayed ABR latencies among factory workers, suggesting that sustained high-intensity noise can compromise auditory function through mechanisms such as neural fatigue and impaired synaptic transmission [10].

Our correlation analysis showed significant relationships between noise exposure levels and

ABR latencies, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.432 to 0.541. These findings corroborate Zheng et al., who demonstrated that higher noise levels led to substantial increases in ABR latencies in a cohort of construction workers [11]. Furthermore, a study by Indora et al., revealed similar trends among traffic policemen in urban areas, reinforcing the notion that chronic noise exposure adversely affects auditory processing capabilities [12]. The explanation for these results lies in the cumulative effects of noise on the central auditory system, where sustained exposure may lead to structural and functional changes that impair the encoding of auditory signals [13].

The high prevalence of self-reported tinnitus (54.4%) and hearing difficulties (44.9%) among traffic police personnel further emphasizes the occupational hazards they face. This is notably higher than rates found in non-traffic settings, where tinnitus rates typically range from 10% to 20% [14]. Studies by Singh et al., and Raja et al.,

have shown similar patterns in urban noise-exposed populations, highlighting a pressing need for awareness regarding the long-term auditory consequences of chronic noise exposure [15,16]. The neurophysiological basis for tinnitus often involves aberrant neural activity in the auditory cortex and alterations in cochlear function, which can be exacerbated by persistent exposure to high-intensity noise [17].

Our study also highlighted significant differences in ABR parameters across various levels of noise exposure. The average noise levels measured (ranging from 84.6 dB in low exposure to 92.4 dB in high exposure) reflect environments linked to noise-induced hearing loss [18]. This correlation suggests that even moderate levels of exposure over extended periods can lead to cumulative auditory damage, reinforcing the need for protective measures. Moreover, findings from Lie et al., and Prendergast et al., demonstrated that regular auditory assessments in high-exposure occupations can lead to early detection and management of hearing-related issues, further supporting our recommendation for ongoing monitoring in this population [19,20].

Limitations

Despite the insights gained, this study has limitations. First, the cross-sectional design limits causal inferences regarding the relationship between noise exposure and auditory dysfunction. Longitudinal studies would better elucidate the long-term effects of chronic noise exposure. Second, reliance on self-reported hearing issues may introduce bias; objective assessments could provide more accurate prevalence rates. Finally, the study's geographic focus on Jammu limits generalizability to other regions with different traffic conditions and noise regulations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our findings underscore the urgent need for intervention strategies to safeguard the auditory health of traffic police personnel. Regular auditory screenings, the provision of protective equipment, and stringent noise regulation measures are critical steps to mitigate the impact of chronic noise exposure. Future research should focus on longitudinal evaluations of these interventions to assess their effectiveness in preventing auditory impairment.

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